

of tillers and panicles per unit area, and reduced number of filled spikelets per panicle.

Regardless of the rice variety used,

good weed control is essential to obtain high grain yield. It is particularly important to weed early-maturing varieties early to minimize yield reduction. The

study also indicated that application of nitrogen fertilizer can increase yields of dry-seeded rice in weed-free conditions,

Weeds of Chingleput district, Tamil Nadu

J. Venkatakrishnan, P. Vivekanandan, and M. Ramachandran, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Tirur – 602025, Tamil Nadu, India

A sound knowledge of weed flora and their possible effects on a crop is essential

when planning weed control measures. Published reports on flora are available, but weed flora on agricultural lands changes. We have compiled a list of all wetland and dryland weeds that grow at PES Tirur (see table).

Tirur receives 1,200 mm average-annual rainfall, most of it during September-

November (northeast monsoon season). Almost no rain falls from January to April. Rice, in wetland and dryland culture, is the major crop. Groundnut and millets also are grown. Weed problems are more severe in drylands than in wetlands. Dry weather from January to April favors the spread of dryland weed seeds that germinate when rains begin in July-August. Rainfed rice grown during July-August face serious weed competition. Weeds that grow during the fallow season cause weeds to spread in wetlands.

Agricultural weeds of Tirur, India.

Dryland weeds

<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> Linn..	Aizoaceae
<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> Linn..	Amaranthaceae
<i>Digera arvensis</i> Forsk.	Amaranthaceae
<i>Gomphrenn celosioides</i> Mart.	Amaranthaceae
<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> Dc. (Linn.)	Asteraceae
<i>Eclipta alba</i> (Linn.) Hassk..	Asteraceae
<i>Erigeron asteroides</i> Roxb.	Asteraceae
<i>Flaveria australasica</i> Hook.	Asteraceae
<i>Lactuca runcinata</i> Dc.	Asteraceae
<i>Tridax procumbens</i> Linn.	Asteraceae
<i>Vernonia cinerea</i> (Linn.) Less..	Asteraceae
<i>Vicoa indica</i> Dc..	Asteraceae
<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> Linn..	Boraginaceae
<i>Trichodesmo indicum</i> R. Br..	Boraginaceae
<i>Eleome viscosa</i> Linn.	Capparidaceae
<i>Gynandropsis pentaphylla</i> (Linn.) Dc.	Capparidaceae
<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (Linn.) Linn..	Convolvulaceae
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn.	Cyperaceae
<i>Fimbristylis littoralis</i> Gaudich.	Cyperaceae
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> Linn.	Euphorbiaceae
<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i> Linn.	Euphorbiaceae
<i>Glinus oppositifolius</i> Linn. A. Dc.	Molluginaceae
<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> Linn..	Nyctaginaceae
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (Linn.) Beauv..	Poaceae
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (Linn.) Link..	Poaceae
<i>Eragrostis interrupta</i> (Lam.) Doell. var. Koenigii. Stapf	Poaceae
<i>Panicumrepens</i> Linn	Poaceae
<i>Sporobolus coromandelianus</i> (Retz.) Kunth.	Poaceae
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> Linn.	Portulacaceae
<i>Hedyotis umbellata</i> Linn. Lam.	Rubiaceae
<i>Rysanthes veronicaefolia</i> Urban.	Scrophulariaceae
<i>Physalis minima</i> Linn.	Solanaceae
<i>Corchorus olitorius</i> Linn.	Tiliaceae

Wetland weeds

<i>Eclipta alba</i> (Linn.) Hassk..	Asteraceae
<i>Cyperus bulbosus</i> Vahl.	Cyperaceae
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> Linn.	Cyperaceae
<i>Fimbristylis miliaceae</i> (Linn.) Vahl.	Cyperaceae
<i>Bergia capensis</i> Linn.	Elatinaceae
<i>Spirodela polyrhiza</i> (Linn.) Schleid.	Lemnaceae
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> Linn..	Lythraceae
<i>Rotala densiflora</i> (Roth.) Koehne.	Lythraceae
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L. Rich.) Pers.	Poaceae
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (Linn.) Link..	Poaceae
<i>Panicum repens</i> Linn..	Poaceae
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	Sphenocleaceae

Soil and crop management

Age of dhaincha, green matter, and nitrogen economy in rice

C. S. Khind, O. P. Meelu, and Viraj Beri, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana, India

In recent work at the PAU farm, burying 2-month-old dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) 1 day before transplanting saved up to 120 kg N/ha. But the period for raising a dhaincha crop varies with time of rice transplanting, generally spread over almost a month in Ludhiana.

The effect of age of dhaincha on amount of green matter added and N economy was tested in kharif 1981. Soil of the experimental plot was loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with a percolation rate of 6 mm/hour. It had pH 8.4, EC 0.15 mmho/cm, 0.34% organic carbon, 0.06% N, 8 µg/gram KCl-extractable NH₄⁺-N, and 8 µg/gram NO₃-N.

Dhaincha was sown at 15-day intervals from 3 May to 3 June to attain 60, 45, and 30-day-old crops at rice transplanting. Phosphorus at 60 kg P₂O₅/ha was applied at sowing. Check plots

Effect of age of dhaincha on green and dry matter production and nitrogen added, Ludhiana, India.

Age of dhaincha (days)	Green matter (t/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	N added (kg/ha)
30	1.6	0.23	8.3
45	15.6	2.03	57.9
60	28.9	5.58	132.0

without dhaincha received basal P applied to rice. The dhaincha crops were buried one day before transplanting on 4 July.

Amount of green matter, dry matter, and N added increased with increasing dhaincha age (see table). In effect on yield, 60-day-old dhaincha alone was equal to 120 kg N/ha applied as urea; 45-day-old dhaincha was equal to 60 kg N/ha; 30-day-old dhaincha did not increase yield substantially (see figure). □

Effect of age of dhaincha green manure on N economy in rice. Ludhiana, India.

Improvement of crop stand in flooded rice fields

B. B. Reddy, B. C. Ghosh, and M. M. Panda, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006 Orissa, India

Direct-seeded rice fields inundated soon after seeding — not infrequent in rainfed lowlands — show suboptimal stands. In controlled greenhouse investigations on improving the germination and crop stand for such situations, seeds soaked in a 1% solution of oxidizing chemicals such as hydrogen peroxide, potassium permanganate, or potassium dichromate for 24 hours were sown in moist soil and immediately flooded with 10, 20, and 40 cm water.

Seeds soaked in hydrogen peroxide and potassium permanganate showed higher germination (90-95%) under different floodwater depths. Seeds soaked in potassium dichromate had drastically reduced germination (40-50%). Seeds soaked in hydrogen peroxide produced vigorous seedlings that emerged rapidly, even from 40-cm-deep floodwater.

The study indicates the possibility of improving crop stands in direct-sown flooded ricefields by soaking the seed in hydrogen peroxide and potassium permanganate. □

Effect of azolla manuring with nitrogen fertilization

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, India

The effect on rice grain yield of incorporating azolla into soil fertilized with nitrogen was studied in a field trial during 1979 rabi. The azolla levels tested were 0, 10, 20, and 30 t/ha; the N fertilizer levels, 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha; and the rice variety, ADT 31. Azolla levels formed the main treatment and nitrogen levels, the subtreatment. The treatments were repli-

cated twice. Azolla was incorporated 1 week before planting; nitrogen as urea was applied in one basal dose. P₂O₅ and K₂O at 50 kg/ha were applied just before planting. The addition of azolla at all levels and of nitrogen at all levels gave significantly higher yields (see table). □

Effect of azolla manuring along with nitrogen applications on grain yield of ADT 31, 1979 rabi, Aduthurai, India

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean (N levels)
	with azolla incorporated at				
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	30 t/ha	
0	3.4	3.8	4.2	4.6	4.0
25	3.8	4.4	4.7	5.0	4.5
50	4.2	4.7	5.3	5.6	4.9
75	4.5	5.3	5.8	6.1	5.4
100	5.0	6.0	6.4	6.8	6.0
Mean (azolla levels)	4.2	4.8	5.3	5.4	
C.D.	Azolla levels 0.3		N levels 0.2		Interaction N.S.

Performance of rice transplanted under nonpuddled rainfed conditions

Y. S. Veeraraja Urs, junior agronomist, A. P. Vishwanath, research assistant, and M. A. Singlachar, rice agronomist, University of Agricultural Sciences, Regional Research Station, Mandya 571405, India

Ragi *Eleusine coracana G.*, an important millet crop of Karnataka, is transplanted on the sides of ridges, then irrigated. A study was conducted to determine whether like ragi, rice could be transplanted under nonpuddled conditions and whether the subsequent rice crop could be grown under rainfed conditions, and given protective irrigation where necessary. A successful crop under these conditions would mean considerable water savings.

The test field was tilled during the early rains of the season. Ridges 20 cm